

Recommendations for the System 9 model

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1. Executive summary

Météo-France is releasing the next generation of its seasonal forecasting system called System 9. This is the final product of more than three years of technical and scientific developments based on the coupled climate model CNRM-CM (Voldoire et al, 2019). Part of these developments were funded by the C3S2_370_MF contract within Work Package 3 (WP3) dedicated to the evolution of the seasonal forecasting system. The present deliverable is the conclusion of Task 3.1 from WP3, focusing on the evolution of the coupled model components. It describes the modeling choices for the atmosphere, ocean, sea-ice and land surface component of CNRM-CM that were retained to make seasonal forecasts with System 9. It also provides the scientific and technical reasons that led to these choices. The coupled model components of System 9 are the following:

- Atmosphere: ARPEGE-Climat version 6.5, including PCMT convection scheme and ecRad radiation scheme;
- Ocean: NEMO 4.2;
- Sea-ice: SI³;
- Land surface component: SURFEX v8.0 incorporating the ISBA land surface model and the CTRIP river routing model, without interactive vegetation.

2. Introduction

The current Météo-France seasonal forecasting system 8 (Batté et al, 2021) is based on the CNRM-CM global coupled climate model (Voldoire et al, 2019) which incorporates the following components:

- The atmosphere model is ARPEGE-Climat, version 6.4.2;
- The ocean model is NEMO, version 3.6;
- The sea-ice model embedded in NEMO is GELATO, version 6;
- The surface interface is SURFEX v8.0, incorporating the ISBA land surface model and the CTRIP river routing model;
- All these model components are coupled using the OASIS3-MCT software.

The new global coupled model used by Météo-France for the next version of its seasonal forecasting System 9 is based on the same architecture, but some model components are updated or changed. In an interim report delivered in May 2023 (Deliverable D3.1.1, Guérémy et al, 2023), several options were considered for the ocean, sea-ice and atmosphere models, as well as the representation of additional processes in the land surface. The present deliverable is a follow-up finalizing Task 3.1 of the C3S2_370_MF contract, describing the analyses leading to the retained options. Section 3 is dedicated to the ocean and sea-ice, while Section 4 focuses on the atmosphere. A brief reminder of the considered land surface evolution that were eventually not included is provided in Section 5. Finally, Section 6 summarizes the recommendations for the System 9 model.

3. Ocean and sea-ice

3.1 NEMO 4.2 and SI³

Parameterization	NEMO 3.6 (System 8)	NEMO 4.2 (System 9)
Sea-ice surface conditions	Embedded (pressure + mass, salt exchanges)	Levitating (no pressure, mass and salt exchanges)
Advection scheme for tracers	TVD scheme (Total Variance Dissipation)	FCT scheme (Flux Corrected Transport)

Table 1: Summary of the main changes in ocean modeling between System 8 and System 9.

Parameterization	GELATO v6 (System 8)	SI ³ (System 9)
Number of ice thickness categories	5	5
Number of ice layers in vertical	5	2
Number of snow layers	1	1
Sea-ice dynamics	Elastic-Viscous-Plastic rheology (EVP)	Adaptive EVP rheology
Minimum ice thickness	0.2	0.1
Maximum ice fraction	0.995	0.997
Melt ponds computation	Deactivated	Deactivated
Thermal conductivity of snow	0.30	0.50
Dry snow albedo	0.84	0.87
Melting snow albedo	0.77	0.82
Dry ice albedo	0.65	0.78
Melting ice albedo	0.56	0.65
Specific albedo computation for thin ice	Deactivated	Deactivated

Table 2: Summary of the main characteristics in sea-ice modeling in System 8 and System 9.

Following work within the CNRM climate modeling group, the version 4.2 of the NEMO ocean model (Madec et al, 2023) has been coupled to the other components of CNRM-CM. This is a more recent version compared to NEMO 3.6 previously used in Météo-France System 8. The NEMO 4.2 ocean model integrates a sea-ice model building on the collaboration of several research teams, named SI³

(Vancoppenolle et al, 2023). Evaluations of this sea-ice model, as well as contributions from CNRM and Mercator Ocean International colleagues to the development of SI³, led to use this model instead of the in-house GELATO model used in previous systems. At the time of interim report D3.1.1, the NEMO 4.2 and SI³ models had only been tested in a standalone mode, forced by an atmosphere reanalysis. Since then, NEMO 4.2 has been tested in a seasonal forecasting context when coupled to the latest version of ARPEGE-Climat (v6.5).

The main characteristics or changes between the NEMO 3.6 and NEMO 4.2 are summarized in Table 1, while the main differences between GELATO and SI³ are summarized in Table 2.

Note that while the choice of the older NEMO 3.6 + GELATO models or the more recent NEMO 4.2 + SI³ models was theoretically left open in D3.1.1, we strongly favor the more recent models for technical reasons. Indeed, NEMO 3.6 and GELATO are no longer maintained on a regular basis, and might be more difficult to port on new supercomputers when those at Météo-France are renewed in 2027. Moreover, NEMO 4.2 benefits from the computation performance improvements introduced through the evolutions between NEMO 3.x and NEMO 4.x versions. The following sections are therefore intended to confirm the choice of updating to NEMO 4.2 + SI³, by showing they are fit for seasonal forecasting purposes. A specific focus has been put on the generation of sea-ice initial conditions and the surface biases.

3.2 Generation of sea-ice initial conditions

Figure 1: Sea-ice thickness (in m) averaged over the Arctic region (latitude > 60°N) from 1993 to 2014, in the PIOMAS reference data (solid black) and in the in-house forced and nudged oceanic simulations providing the sea-ice initial conditions for seasonal forecasts. Dashed cyan: forced and nudged simulation using NEMO 3.6 and GELATO, as in System 8. Solid red: forced and nudged simulation using NEMO 4.2 and SI³.

Sea-ice initial conditions of System 8 are prepared separately from the initial conditions of the other coupled model components. They come from an ocean-only simulation where NEMO is both nudged towards the Copernicus Marine Service ocean reanalysis GLORYS12V1 in temperature and salinity, and forced at the surface by fluxes from the C3S atmosphere reanalysis ERA5 (Hersbach et

al., 2020). Other investigations (to be detailed in the companion deliverable D3.2.1 on initialization and ensemble generation) have shown that the same methodology should still be implemented in the case of System 9 to have realistic sea-ice initial states. In this context, Figure 1 demonstrates that a forced and nudged ocean-only run based on NEMO 4.2 and SI³ provides better sea-ice initial states – relative to the PIOMAS reference data (Schweiger et al, 2011) – than a similar run based on NEMO 3.6 and GELATO. This is an additional reason, beyond the technical considerations, for changing the ocean and sea-ice models in System 9.

3.3 Surface biases in coupled mode for seasonal forecasting

Figure 2: Sea surface temperature biases (in K) in System 8 (left column) and in two reforecast experiments using NEMO 4.2 and SI³, over the 1993-2018 reforecast period. Upper row: JJA bias (init. May). Lower row: DJF bias (init. November). The mean absolute bias between 60°S and 60°N is indicated in the title of each panel. Reference: ERA5.

Twin seasonal reforecast experiments using the NEMO 4.2 and SI³ models coupled to ARPEGE-Climat v6.5 were performed, and compared to the current System 8 using NEMO 3.6 and GELATO. This comparison is provided in Figure 2 for the sea surface temperature (SST) biases over the main target seasons JJA and DJF, after the May and November initializations. The two reforecast experiments only differ in atmospheric physics options to be described in Section 4, such that their shared benefits relative to System 8 can be at least partly attributed to the update in ocean modeling. Judging by Figure 2, one of these shared benefits seems to be the reduction of the SST mean absolute bias. Indeed, this SST mean absolute bias with respect to ERA5, for which values are inserted in the panel titles, is reduced in both experiments with respect to System 8 (with a substantial difference for the May initialization). This can be explained by the removal of some warm SST biases that System 8 exhibits with NEMO 3.6, i.e. in the Northern Hemisphere in JJA and in the Southern Hemisphere in

DJF . This suggests that switching from NEMO 3.6 to NEMO 4.2 tends to “cool down” the ocean in the coupled model and therefore decreases the average bias. This result also supports the use of NEMO 4.2 for System 9.

4. Atmosphere

4.1 Two options for atmospheric physics

As already introduced in Deliverable D3.1.1, two options were considered for atmospheric physics. These are referred to as P6+ and P7, and their main differences compared to the ARPEGE physics of System 8 (called P6) are listed in Table 3. In a nutshell, both options provide updates when it comes to the radiation scheme that is changed to ecRad, while they differ in terms of convection schemes. P6+ is the more conservative option as it uses the PCMT unified convection scheme similar to System 8, while P7 relies on different convection modeling choices. Note that the interim report D3.1.1 also considered additional modifications of the turbulence scheme in P6+ that were eventually removed, because they worsened the warm SST biases in the Eastern boundaries of tropical oceans (not shown).

Parameterization	System 8 (P6)	P6+	P7
Radiation	Longwave: Mlawer et al (1997) Shortwave: Morcrette (1990)	ecRad (Hogan and Bozzo, 2016)	ecRad (Hogan and Bozzo, 2016)
Deep convection	PCMT (Piriou et al 2007, Gueremy 2011)	PCMT (Piriou et al 2007, Gueremy 2011)	IFS deep convection (Bechtold et al, 2014)
Shallow convection	PCMT	PCMT	Pergaud et al (2009)
Turbulence	Cuxart et al (2000)	Cuxart et al (2000)*	Cuxart et al (2000)

Table 3: Summary of the main modifications in the atmosphere physics between Météo-France System 8 and the two candidate physics for System 9.

*In a previously tested version of P6+, there were modifications of the turbulence scheme that are not retained: smaller mixing length close to the surface, heating due to Turbulent Kinetic Energy dissipation

Twin seasonal reforecast experiments, already mentioned in Section 3.3, were carried out when P6+ or P7 atmospheric physics are activated in the CNRM-CM coupled model along with NEMO 4.2 and SI³. The details are as follows:

- Reforecast period: 1993-2018
- Initializations on 1 May and 1 November
- Initial conditions:
 - ERA5 for the atmosphere and land surface,

- In-house simulation for ocean and sea-ice: an ocean-only run forced by ERA5 at the surface, and nudged towards the ocean reanalysis GLORYS12V1 from Mercator Ocean International
 - Ensemble size: 15 members
 - Ensemble generation: perturbation of atmospheric initial conditions

Both reforecast experiments are assessed in terms of mean bias and forecast scores against ERA5 (Hersbach et al, 2020) as a reference dataset, except for precipitation for which the reference is MSWEP v2 (Beck et al, 2017).

4.2 Comparison of atmospheric and SST biases

Figure 3 illustrates the DJF biases of near-surface temperature (T2m), precipitation (RR) and geopotential height at 500 hPa (Z500) in the two experiments and in System 8. The counterpart of Figure 3 for JJA season is provided in Appendix (Figure 10).

Figure 3: Atmospheric DJF biases (init. November) in System 8 (left column) and in the two reforecast experiments using P6+ and P7, over the 1993-2018 reforecast period. Upper row: near-surface temperature at 2 m. Middle row: precipitation. Lower row: geopotential height at 500 hPa. The mean absolute bias is indicated in the title of each panel. For temperature (upper row), the mean absolute bias is restricted to the 60°S-60°N band, and the second value indicates the bias on land grid-points only.

The overall result of Figures 3 and 10 is that seasonal forecasts with the P7 atmospheric physics have more biases than those with the P6+ physics. This is particularly striking for Z500, for which P7

exhibits a systematic positive bias all around the tropical band that does not exist in System 8 and P6+. This is also notable for the warm T2m bias over Eurasia in DJF, that is the strongest in P7. The picture is more contrasted for precipitation where all models exhibit dipolar or tripolar bias structures revealing misplaced convergence zones, but the overall bias of P7 for this variable is still greater than that of System 8 and P6+, on account of wet biases over the Indian ocean and Maritime Continent.

The comparison of SST biases has already been illustrated in Figure 2, which shows reasonable SST biases for P6+ and P7, although the mean absolute SST bias is slightly better for P6+. In order to go deeper, we analyze the SST biases in the Niño3.4 box, that are illustrated in Figure 4 for every monthly lead time after the May and November initializations. It appears in Figure 4 that both P6+ and P7 are affected by drifts of opposite sign in the May initializations, making them both worse than System 8 on this aspect. As for the November initialization, the P7 physics is also affected by a negative drift, although the magnitude of this drift is smaller than in May.

Figure 4: Mean bias (in K) of the Niño3.4 monthly mean sea surface temperature in the System 8 reforecasts (cyan), the P6+ reforecast experiment (blue) and the P7 reforecast experiment (red), over the 1993-2018 period. Left panel: May initialization. Right panel: November initialization. Reference: ERA5.

4.3 Comparison of forecast scores

In order to get an overview of forecast performance in each reforecast (System 8, P6+ and P7), we use the meanACC score over several spatial domains: Southern Hemisphere (90°S-30°S), Inter-tropical (30°S-30°N), Northern Hemisphere (30°N-90°N), Euro-Atlantic (85.5°W-35.5°E; 27.5°N-80.5°N) and Europe (29.5°W-40.5°W; 30.5°N-70.5°N). The meanACC metric is defined in Déqué and Royer (1992) and quantifies the aggregated spatial and temporal association between the forecasts and observations on the chosen domain. The variables under verification are T2m, precipitation and Z500. The Euro-Atlantic domain is used for Z500 only, while the Europe domain only applies to T2m and precipitation. These domains have been chosen as additional diagnostics targeting the main region of interest for the seasonal forecast bulletins at Météo-France.

Figure 5 shows how the new atmospheric physics P6+ and P7, coupled to NEMO 4.2 and SI³, compare to the operational System 8 in terms of meanACC for the target seasons JJA and DJF at a lead time of 1 month. The uncertainty of the scores related to the years in the sample is assessed

through a bootstrap procedure, where each score is computed 1,000 times from 26 random years drawn with replacement in the 1993-2018 period. The solid bars indicate the median of the bootstrap and the error bars indicate the 5%-95% confidence interval.

The bootstrap is also used for significance testing of the differences between two scores: if the difference in meanACC between P6+ and System 8 is positive for more than 95% of the bootstrap draws, then the meanACC of P6+ is considered significantly greater than that of System 8. Figure 5 shows significant differences as triangles, where an upward-pointing (resp. downward-pointing) triangle above a bar means that the score indicated by this bar is significantly greater (resp. less) than the score in the neighboring bar which has the same color as the triangle. For instance, the middle left panel of Figure 5 (precipitation meanACC for May initialization) shows that the meanACC of P6+ is significantly greater than that of System 8 in the Tropics. Yet, in spite of this significance testing, Figure 5 shows no clear advantage to one of the P6+ or P7 physics compared to another.

Figure 5: meanACC scores of the System 8 reforecasts (cyan), the P6+ reforecast experiment (blue) and the P7 reforecast experiment (red), over the 1993-2018 period and various spatial domains. The error bars indicate the 5%-95% confidence interval of each score, estimated through a bootstrap over the reforecast years (1,000 draws with replace of the years from 1993 to 2018). See text for details on the upward and downward-pointing triangles. References: ERA5 (T2m, Z500) and MSWEP (precipitation).

Besides forecast skill on atmospheric variables, the three reforecasts are also compared in terms of ENSO prediction using temporal correlation and Mean Absolute Error (MAE) for the Niño3.4 sea surface temperature anomalies, at monthly lead times. While temporal correlation assesses the ability of the forecast system to predict the interannual variability of the ENSO phenomenon, the Mean Absolute Error quantifies how close the predicted Niño3.4 anomalies will be to the observed ones.

Figure 6 suggests that both P6+ and P7 maintain a satisfactory predictive ability of ENSO compared to System 8, with temporal correlations that are either similar or greater. The benefits of P6+ compared to System 8 are significant for both initializations in the months 2 to 4. However, note that the P6+ and P7 experiments are based on temporary initialization and ensemble generation methods, such that the gains in skill might not be exactly those of the final System 9.

Figure 6: Temporal correlation of the Niño3.4 monthly mean sea surface temperature reforecasts of System 8 (cyan), P6+ (blue) and P7 (red), in the six months after the May (left panel) and November (right panel) initializations, over the 1993-2018 period. Significant differences are estimated through a bootstrap procedure and indicated with triangles as in Figure 5 (see text for details). Reference: ERA5.

Figure 7: Mean Absolute Error (in K) of the Niño3.4 monthly mean sea surface temperature reforecasts in System 8 (cyan), P6+ (blue) and P7 (red), over the 1993-2018 period. Left panel: May initialization. Right panel: November initialization. Reference: ERA5.

As a complement to correlation, Figure 7 shows the Mean Absolute Error of Niño3.4 SST. It is notable from Figure 7 that Niño3.4 SST anomaly errors develop less rapidly in P6+ than P7, especially

in the November initialization. Note that the Mean Absolute Errors are insensitive to any mean bias in the models since they are computed on anomalies, such that the differences between P6+ and P7 on Figure 7 indeed reveal a difference in predictive ability. This is illustrated in Figure 8, showing the Niño3.4 forecast anomalies around two big El Niño events. The first panel of Figure 8 shows that P7 starting in May 2015 is widely overestimating the growing positive SST anomalies prior to the 2015-2016 El Niño while System 8 and P6+ are closer to ERA5. Similarly, the second panel shows that P7 overestimates the peak Niño3.4 SST anomaly and struggles to simulate a proper decay of the 1997-1998 El Niño, in the six months following the November 1997 initialization.

Figure 8: Niño3.4 monthly mean sea surface temperature anomalies (in °C) from May to October 2015 (left panel) and from November 1997 to April 1998 (right panel), in the ERA5 reanalysis (dashed black) and in the seasonal reforecasts from System 8 (solid cyan), P6+ (solid blue) and P7 (solid red).

4.4 Retained atmospheric physics

All in all, the comparison between P6+ and P7 in terms of average biases and forecast performance is more favorable to P6+, which is retained for System 9. This choice can be supported by several results shown above, but is mostly motivated by the diagnostics on Niño3.4 sea surface temperature anomalies, which evidence a clear degradation of forecast quality in terms of absolute error with P7 physics despite similar levels of correlation. This flaw of P7 can be attributed to the fact it is not optimally tuned in coupled mode, since it was only recently introduced in the CNRM modeling group, and had never been tested with a coupling to the ocean and land surface prior to our seasonal forecast experiments. As a result, the atmosphere model of System 9 with P6+ is very close to that of System 8, except for the notable change of the radiation scheme to ecRad.

4.5 Update in atmospheric forcings

Greenhouse gas forcings in System 8 are provided by the CMIP6 historical forcings up to 2014, and by the SSP3-7.0 scenario from 2015 onwards. It has been shown that the SSP2-4.5 scenario actually provides the most realistic radiative forcings over the last decade, i.e. after the end of the CMIP6 historical forcings in 2014 (Forster et al, 2024). Consequently, we change the radiative forcings of System 9 to that of SSP2-4.5. This modification only applies to the last years of the reforecast period

from 2015 onwards, and to the real-time forecasts, when historical forcing data is no longer available.

As for aerosols, System 8 uses a seasonally-varying climatology of a historical simulation over the 1995-2014 period. Interim report D3.1.1 investigated the possibility of using an interactive modeling of aerosols for System 9 and concluded that this option was too computationally expensive (+ 40%) with respect to the expected benefits in terms of forecast skill. However, in order to account for the long term evolution of aerosols throughout the historical period and the SSP2-4.5 scenario, we decide to apply a moving average aerosol climatology: the aerosol forcings for year Y and month m are chosen as the 11-year average at month m , from year $Y-5$ to year $Y+5$, coming from a concatenation of historical (up to 2014) and SSP2-4.5 (from 2015 onwards) simulations using the TACTIC interactive aerosol scheme (Michou et al, 2020).

5. Land surface

An interactive modeling of vegetation in seasonal forecasts – represented by the Leaf Area Index (LAI) – has been implemented and studied in the European project H2020 CONFESS (CONSistent representation of temporal variations of boundary Forcings in reanalysES and Seasonal forecasts). Results from the project were intended to inform on possible seasonal forecast evolution with respect to land surface modeling and boundary forcings. However, results from CONFESS with the CNRM-CM coupled model have shown that interactive LAI does not bring a clear added value in terms of forecast skill for surface climate parameters such as T2m. This is illustrated by Figure 9 from CONFESS deliverable D3.3 (Ardilouze, 2024). Given the implications in terms of real-time implementation and computational costs, we therefore considered that the increased complexity of interactive LAI was not mature for implementation in operational System 9.

Figure 9: Difference of T2m temporal correlation between two seasonal reforecast experiments over the 1993-2019 period. The climate model is CNRM-CM similar to System 8 with lower atmospheric ($\sim 1.4^\circ$) and oceanic (1°) resolutions. MF-Int: with interactive LAI. MF-Eco: with climatological LAI. Adapted from CONFESS deliverable D3.3 (Ardilouze, 2024).

6. Conclusion

The coupled climate model for Météo-France seasonal forecasting System 9 is based on the architecture of the CNRM-CM model. The main novelties compared to System 8 are the following:

- Atmosphere: ARPEGE-Climat version 6.5 with a new radiation scheme (ecRad)
- Ocean: a new version of the NEMO model (v 4.2)
- Sea-ice: a new sea-ice model (SI³)

These model updates bring improvements compared to the current System 8, on both scientific and technical aspects:

- Available expertise and support for the ocean and sea-ice models
- Ocean and sea-ice models easier to maintain in the long term
- Reduced biases, especially for SST
- Maintained or improved forecast performance (meanACC scores) compared to System 8
- A slight but significant improvement — to be confirmed in the official reforecasts — for ENSO prediction

This deliverable comes along a companion deliverable D3.2.1 (“Synthesis report on initialization and ensemble generation”) dedicated to the specific seasonal forecasting setup to be implemented with the coupled model chosen for System 9.

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8. Appendix

Figure 10: Atmospheric JJA biases (init. May) in System 8 (left column) and in the two reforecast experiments using P6+ and P7, over the 1993-2018 reforecast period. Upper row: near-surface temperature at 2 m. Middle row: precipitation. Lower row: geopotential height at 500 hPa. The mean absolute bias is indicated in the title of each panel. For temperature (upper row), the mean absolute bias is restricted to the 60°S-60°N band, and the second value indicates the bias on land grid-points only.

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